

Prediction of Several Machine Learning Classification Models to Predict Type 2 Diabetes Diagnosis in Females

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ABSTRACT

Medical and biological sciences are among the many fields greatly impacted by machine learning (ML). Diabetes is a chronic disease characterized by unusually high blood sugar levels and insulin use. The analysis of diabetic patients and the diagnosis of the disease using various ML approaches is the main subject of this research. In this study, ML models were estimated using the PIMA dataset, which consists of female diabetic patients who were at least 21 years old. The relevant dataset was originally provided by the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases. Various diagnostic measurements are included in the dataset. Model performance was evaluated using an exploratory dataset and the 5-fold cross-validation method. The purpose of the dataset is to predict whether a patient has diabetes using diagnostic ML algorithms. In this study, the performance of classifiers such as Naive Bayes (NB), Stochastic Gradient Boosting (SGB), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Logistic Regression (LR) algorithms were compared. According to the results of the performance measurements for diabetes prediction, the Stochastic Gradient Boosting (SGB) model outperformed the other ML algorithms in terms of Accuracy, Balanced Accuracy, F1-Score, Sensitivity, Specificity, Youden index, Positive Predictive Value (PPV), and Negative Predictive Value (NPV).

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes, diabetes prediction, machine learning, classification

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a widespread chronic illness that develops when the body either cannot properly use insulin (Type 2 diabetes T2D) or the pancreas does not create enough insulin (Type 1 diabetes). Increased blood sugar, or hyperglycemia, is a typical side effect of untreated diabetes. Diabetes has the potential to seriously harm blood vessels and nerves over time. Kidney failure, vision impairment, and cardiovascular disease worsen advanced diabetes (Rao Kondapally Seshasai et al., 2011). Following the process of digestion, glucose is released when we eat. A blood hormone called insulin enters cells from the blood and instructs them to utilize blood sugar for energy production. When the pancreas fails to produce sufficient insulin, glucose remains unabsorbed in the blood. Consequently, blood sugar/glucose levels escalate to an intolerable point (Fletcher et al., 2002). Individuals experience symptoms such as severe hunger, excessive thirst, and frequent urination due to elevated blood sugar levels. Normally, the human body contains 70-99 mg of glucose per deciliter. If your blood sugar exceeds 126 mg/dl, you are diagnosed with diabetes. A person's body glucose level falling between 100 and 125 mg/dl is considered prediabetes (Feltman, 2022). Since many persons with diabetes are asymptomatic or unaware of the disease, diabetes frequently goes undiagnosed; roughly one-third of diabetic patients are uninformed of their condition (Choi et al., 2014). Numerous bodily systems and organs, including the kidneys, heart, nerves, blood vessels, and eyes, are seriously harmed over time by uncontrolled diabetes. People who are at risk can therefore take preventive action to stop the disease's progression and enhance their quality of life thanks to enhanced disease diagnosis (Deberneh et al., 2020). Numerous fields of study, such as artificial intelligence (AI) ML, are being investigated to lessen the consequences of diabetes and enhance the standard of patient care (Buch et al., 2018; Woldaregay et al., 2019; Zou et al., 2018). Numerous studies have reported on the use of ML to predict the prevalence of diabetes (Deberneh et al., 2020; Maniruzzaman et al., 2017; Ravaut et al., 2019). These techniques can be divided into two categories: sophisticated forecasting techniques and scenario assessment (screening, diagnosis). While forward prediction approaches use both historical and current medical information to estimate the incidence of diabetes, baseline identification methods focus on identifying existing datasets (Ravaut et al., 2019). ML, is one of the best techniques for building models used in the healthcare industry, especially in disease diagnosis. The goal of ML, a branch of artificial intelligence, is to create models or systems that can learn from pre-existing datasets and then make predictions based on that learning. The healthcare industry uses ML algorithms to analyze massive amounts of data, identify notable trends, and derive important insights. By applying ML algorithms to healthcare data, important information can be obtained that will improve diagnostic decision-making. By recognizing significant patterns throughout the learning process, huge diagnostic datasets can be utilized to train ML models, which eliminates the need for human intervention in decision-making. This may result in less

expensive medical treatment, improved outcomes for patients, and more precise and effective diagnosis (Ray & Chaudhuri, 2021). This study aims to use ML models to diagnostically predict whether women have T2D based on specific diagnostic measures in the dataset.

METHODS

Dataset and related factors

The "Pima Indians Diabetes Database" dataset was downloaded from <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/akshaydattatraykhare/diabetes-dataset> for this study in order to assess the risk factors and investigate the operation of the NB, SGB, XGBoost, and LR models. Of the 768 individuals in the sample, 268 (34.9%) have T2D, while 500 (65.1%) do not (control). The National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases is the original source of this dataset. Based on specific diagnostic metrics included in the dataset, the dataset's goal is to diagnostically forecast whether a patient has diabetes. These examples were chosen from a bigger database under several restrictions. Specifically, all of the patients in this facility are Pima Indian women who are at least 21 years old (Barale & Shirke, 2016; Smith et al., 1988). Information on the data is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Explanations about the variables in the dataset and their properties

Variable/Feature	Description	Type	Role
Pregnancies	Number of pregnancies(1=5 or less,2=5 to 10,3=10 or more)	Categorical	Input
Glucose	2-hour plasma glucose concentration in the oral glucose tolerance test	Quantitative	Input
BloodPressure	Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	Quantitative	Input
SkinThickness	Triceps skinfold thickness (mm)	Quantitative	Input
Insulin	2-hour serum insulin (mu U / ml)	Quantitative	Input
BMI	Body mass index [weight in kg / (height in m) ²]	Quantitative	Input
Diabetes Pedigree Function	Diabetes family tree function	Quantitative	Input
Age	Age (years)	Quantitative	Input
Outcome	Class variable (0: absent, 1: present)	Categorical	Output

Biostatistical Data Analysis

Qualitative variables were summarized by calculating frequency (percentage). The Pearson chi-square test was used to examine the association of qualitative variables with

diabetes. Quantitative variables were summarized by calculating the median, interquartile range (IQR), 95% confidence interval, and effect size (ES). It was observed that the data were not normally distributed. The Mann-Whitney U Test was used to examine the association with diabetes. For all results, $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS 26.0 IBM package program.

The 5-fold cross-validation (CV) method was used to evaluate models predicting type 2 diabetic patients. CV, a technique used to measure the generalizability of a machine learning model to unseen data, involves dividing the dataset into folds, training the model on a subset, and evaluating it on the rest. In a 5-fold CV, the dataset is divided into 5 equal parts, each part is used once for evaluation and the process is repeated 5 times for training. It provides a robust assessment of the model's performance and reduces variability in performance estimates.

Naive Bayes (NB)

The NB algorithm can also be utilized for classifying patient data. For instance, by using patients' demographic information, medical history, and test results, the algorithm can identify which patients have a high risk of developing a particular disease (Jackins et al., 2021). Additionally, the analysis of medical articles, doctors' notes, and other medical texts can be conducted using the NB algorithm. When combined with text mining techniques, the algorithm can analyze the frequency of certain keywords or phrases in the texts and their association with specific diseases or medical conditions (Ananiadou & McNaught, 2006). NB classification is used in text classification, phishing detection, medical diagnosis (Goyal & Maheshwar, 2019), job search engines (Slamet et al., 2018), and spam detection. This algorithm is also characterized by simplicity and acceptable efficiency.

Lojistik Regresyon (LR)

LR is particularly useful when predicting the presence or absence of a condition based on multiple factors. When used in healthcare, it is referred to as the ML method used to predict a patient's risk of developing a disease based on test findings, age, gender and medical history, among other variables (Çolak, 2001). Using patient data, including age, BMI, glucose levels, and other clinical measures, logistic regression is used to estimate the probability of T2D. It has a high accuracy rate for predicting the risk of diabetes, according to studies. For instance, an analysis with 78.26% prediction accuracy utilizing the Pima Indian Diabetes dataset showed important variables such as BMI and glucose levels (Joshi & Dhakal, 2021).

eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

Gradient boosting, one of the ML techniques, is a method used for regression and classification problems. This technique produces an ensemble model by combining weak predictive models, typically decision trees. Gradient boosting aims to create strong

predictive models by utilizing boosting techniques. This method enhances the model's performance by minimizing errors at each step, thereby yielding more accurate predictions (Akbulut et al., 2022; Dikker, 2017). XGBoost is an advanced version of the gradient boosting algorithm. It is widely used in ML approaches and practical applications due to its efficiency, accurate classification, and effective scalability. The method builds an ensemble of decision trees sequentially, where each new tree aims to improve the errors made by the previous trees (Chen & Guestrin, 2016).

Stochastic Gradient Boosting (SGB)

SGB, developed by Friedman, incorporates randomness into the traditional gradient boosting method. In this approach, a random subsample is selected at each iteration using a permutation sampling strategy. This subsample, rather than the entire dataset, is used to calculate the model update. This technique helps reduce the correlation between trees and enhances the model's robustness (Friedman, 2002). Similar to other ensemble learning techniques, stochastic gradient boosting does not create large trees. Instead, it develops a large number of smaller trees (typically 100-200), each contributing to the final model. The predictions from each tree are aggregated, and each observation is classified based on the most frequent prediction across the ensemble. This method differentiates itself from other boosting techniques through its incorporation of randomness, which helps to reduce the sensitivity to outliers and handle unbalanced datasets more effectively. Additionally, by focusing on smaller trees and leveraging random subsampling, stochastic gradient boosting enhances model robustness and generalization. This approach mitigates overfitting and improves performance on diverse datasets (Friedman, 2002; Lawrence et al., 2004).

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics for qualitative and quantitative factors are presented in Table 2. Among the 768 individuals in the sample, 268 (34.9%) had T2D, while 500 (65.1%) did not. The quantitative factor of pregnancy status was categorized into three groups: 5 or fewer pregnancies, 5 to 10 pregnancies, and 10 or more pregnancies. The potential for having T2D was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, statistically significant differences were observed between the groups with respect to Glucose, Blood Pressure, Skin Thickness, BMI, Diabetes Pedigree Function, and Age ($p < 0.001$). The statistically significant variables were calculated to have a high effect size.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for diabetes factors

Variable	Group				ES	p-value
	Control		Diabetes			
	Median(IQR)	95% Confidence Interval	Median(IQR)	95% Confidence Interval		
Glucose	107(32)	151-164	140(48)	187-196	1.081	<0.001*
blood pressure	70(16)	90-94	74(16)	90-104	0.288	<0.001*
SkinThickness	21(31)	41-45	27(36)	45-49	0.178	<0.001*
Insulin	39(105)	210-310	0(168)	300-4	0.125	0.066*
BMI	30.1(9.9)	40.6-44.2	34.3(8.1)	45.4-49.7	0.651	<0.001*
DiabetesPedigreeFunction	0.34(0.33)	0.88-1.1	0.45(0.47)	1.14-1.35	0.356	<0.001*
Age	27(14)	55-63	36(16)	54-62	0.649	<0.001*
Pregnancies	Categories	N(%)	N(%)		0.209	<0.001**
	5 or fewer pregnant	392(78.4)	157(58.6)			
	5 to 10 pregnant	80(16)	81(30.2)			
	10 or more pregnant	28(5.6)	30(11.2)			

*: Mann-Whitney U Test; **: Pearson chi-square test; IQR: Inter Quantile Range; ES: effect size

A comparative analysis of the performance of the four ML models NB, LR, XGBoost and SGB in classifying T2D patients is given in Table 3. The evaluation criteria included accuracy, balanced accuracy, F1 score, sensitivity, specificity, Youden index, Positive Predictive Value (PPV) and Negative Predictive Value (NPV). Among these classifiers, the SGB model demonstrated superior performance across all metrics, making it the most effective model for predicting T2D in our study. Specifically, the SGB model exhibited exceptionally high sensitivity [0.982 (0.966 - 0.992)], indicating its ability to correctly identify 98.2% of individuals with T2D. Furthermore, the SGB model achieved high accuracy [0.951 (0.935 - 0.966)], PPV [0.944 (0.921 - 0.962)], and NPV [0.964 (0.932 - 0.983)], underscoring its robustness and reliability in predicting T2D. The consistently high performance of the SGB model across these critical metrics highlights its potential utility in clinical settings for early and accurate identification of T2D patients. The XGBoost model demonstrated impressive performance in predicting T2D, achieving an accuracy score of 0.901 (95% CI: 0.88 - 0.922) and an F1 score of 0.926 (95% CI: 0.907 - 0.944). When compared to the other prediction models—Naive Bayes (NB), Logistic Regression (LR), and Stochastic Gradient Boosting (SGB)—the XGBoost model consistently outperformed them. The XGBoost model's evaluation metrics are as follows: sensitivity of 0.948 (95% CI: 0.925 - 0.966), balanced accuracy of 0.881 (95% CI: 0.858 - 0.904), specificity of 0.813 (95% CI: 0.762 - 0.858), Youden's index of 0.761 (95% CI: 0.686 - 0.824), Positive Predictive Value (PPV) of 0.905 (95% CI: 0.876 - 0.928), and Negative Predictive Value (NPV) of 0.893 (95% CI: 0.848 - 0.929). These results indicate that the XGBoost model not only has a high

sensitivity, meaning it correctly identifies a significant proportion of patients with T2D, but also maintains a balanced accuracy, reflecting its effectiveness in distinguishing between diabetic and non-diabetic individuals. The specificity indicates the model's capability to correctly identify non-diabetic individuals, reducing the rate of false positives. Moreover, the high values for PPV and NPV demonstrate the model's reliability in predicting both the presence and absence of T2D, respectively. Youden's index further highlights the model's balanced performance in terms of sensitivity and specificity. In conclusion, the superior performance metrics of the SGB model underscore its robustness and efficacy in the prediction of T2D, making it a valuable tool in clinical decision-making and patient management.

Table 3. Results of performance measures for diabetes prediction of the models

Model	Accuracy	Balanced accuracy	F1-Score	Sensitivity	Specificity	Youden's index	PPV	NPV
NB	0.762 (0.732 - 0.792)	0.727 (0.695 - 0.758)	0.821 (0.794 - 0.849)	0.842 (0.807 - 0.873)	0.612 (0.551 - 0.671)	0.454 (0.358 - 0.543)	0.802 (0.765 - 0.835)	0.675 (0.612 - 0.733)
LR	0.783 (0.753 - 0.812)	0.736 (0.705 - 0.767)	0.842 (0.816 - 0.868)	0.89 (0.859 - 0.916)	0.582 (0.521 - 0.642)	0.472 (0.38 - 0.558)	0.799 (0.763 - 0.831)	0.739 (0.675 - 0.797)
XGBoost	0.901 (0.88 - 0.922)	0.881 (0.858 - 0.904)	0.926 (0.907 - 0.944)	0.948 (0.925 - 0.966)	0.813 (0.762 - 0.858)	0.761 (0.686 - 0.824)	0.905 (0.876 - 0.928)	0.893 (0.848 - 0.929)
SGB	0.951 (0.935 - 0.966)	0.937 (0.92 - 0.954)	0.963 (0.949 - 0.976)	0.982 (0.966 - 0.992)	0.892 (0.848 - 0.926)	0.874 (0.814 - 0.918)	0.944 (0.921 - 0.962)	0.964 (0.932 - 0.983)

SGB: Stochastic Gradient Boosting; XGBoost: eXtreme Gradient Boosting; LR: logistic regression; PPV: Positive predictive value; NPV: negative predictive value; Metrics are summarized with mean and 95% confidence interval

DISCUSSION

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disease characterized by elevated blood glucose levels. Among the various types of diabetes, T2D is the most prevalent. Early diagnosis and effective treatment are critical in preventing or delaying the onset of associated complications (Agliata et al., 2023). This paper examines the application of ML techniques for the prediction of diabetes, highlighting the potential of these advanced methods to improve early detection and intervention strategies. By leveraging large datasets and sophisticated algorithms, ML can provide significant insights into the risk factors and patterns associated with the development of T2D, thereby enhancing predictive accuracy and facilitating timely medical responses. It presents experimental results of ML models used for model prediction. The algorithms used in this study include NB, LR, XGBoost, and SGB. The performance of these models was evaluated using various metrics such as accuracy, balanced accuracy, F1-score, sensitivity, specificity, Youden index, PPV, and

NPV. According to the performance criteria calculated in this study, the SGB model provided superior prediction results compared to the NB, LR, and XGBoost models in the classification of T2D. The high precision of the SGB model [0.982 (95% CI: 0.966 - 0.992)] indicates that it can accurately identify 98.2% of individuals with T2D. Additionally, the SGB model achieved high accuracy [0.951 (95% CI: 0.935 - 0.966)], PPV [0.944 (95% CI: 0.921 - 0.962)], and NPV [0.964 (95% CI: 0.932 - 0.983)]. In a study utilizing the same dataset, the performance criteria for accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity when using SVM were 78%, 80%, and 76.5%, respectively (Kumari & Chitra, 2013). Another study employing the same dataset used six different ML models for classification. Among these models, the Hoeffding Tree algorithm demonstrated the best classification performance, with precision, recall, and F1-score values of 0.757, 0.762, and 0.759, respectively (Mercaldo et al., 2017). In a study using the same dataset, the performance values obtained with the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) were accuracy 78.1%, specificity 81.2%, sensitivity 71%, PPV 61.7%, PPV 86.8% and F-score 66%. The performance measures for the Radial Basis Function(RBF) model are 76.8%, 82.1%, 66.0%, 66.0%, 64.6%, 83%, 83% and 65.3% for the accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, PPV, NPV and F-score, respectively (Güldoğan et al., 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the experimental results of ML models used for predicting T2D. The algorithms evaluated in this study include NB, LR, XGBoost, SGB. The performance of these models was assessed using a variety of metrics, including accuracy, balanced accuracy, F1-score, sensitivity, specificity, Youden's index, PPV, and NPV.

The findings indicate that the SGB model yielded superior prediction results compared to the NB, LR, and XGBoost models in classifying T2D. The SGB model demonstrated higher accuracy and precision across all evaluated metrics. The precision of the SGB model was particularly notable, with a value of 0.982 (95% CI: 0.966 - 0.992), indicating that it correctly identified 98.2% of individuals with T2D. Additionally, the SGB model achieved an accuracy of 0.951 (95% CI: 0.935 - 0.966), a PPV of 0.944 (95% CI: 0.921 - 0.962), and an NPV of 0.964 (95% CI: 0.932 - 0.983). Overall, these results underscore the efficacy of the SGB model in accurately predicting T2D, outperforming other commonly used machine learning algorithms. This highlights the potential of the SGB model as a robust tool for early diagnosis and intervention in T2D, offering significant improvements in predictive accuracy and reliability

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, F.H.Y. methodology, F.H.Y, A.P.; formal analysis, A.P.; investigation, A.P.; data curation, F.Y.H.; writing—original draft preparation, F.H.Y, A.P.; writing—review and editing, F.H.Y, A.P.

Informed Consent Statement:

The research was conducted in line with the Declaration of Helsinki.

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Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare that no conflicts interest.

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